

Wide rows spaced 53 cm alternated with narrow rows 13.6 cm apart. The distance between hills in 1 row was 6.6 cm.

Fresh azolla (*A. pinnata*) amounting to 13-18 kg was inoculated into a plot. A total of 53 kg superphosphate/ha was applied — half before transplanting and the rest at the time of each azolla inoculation. All plots were supplied with equal amounts of phosphate. Carbofuran (3% a.i.) at 1 g/m² was broadcast on the azolla inoculum.

After 15 to 20 days, azolla covered the paddy water surface. The water was drained for 2-3 days to make the azolla adhere to the soil surface. Then the azolla was incorporated into the soil by feet, hand weeder, or rake. A fresh

inoculum was applied with superphosphate and insecticide. This allowed azolla to grow 4-6 times during one crop of rice. In the second trial azolla was not grown after rice had headed because the paddy surface was shaded and azolla growth was poor.

To study the effect of azolla incorporation, three treatments — no nitrogen, with chemical nitrogen, and with azolla — were compared (see table). Ammonium sulfate was applied before transplanting and incorporated into the soil. The plots were arranged in a Latin square.

The response of the first rice crop to azolla incorporation was apparent only at late stages of growth. No yield increase from azolla incorporation was

observed probably because soil fertility was high. In the second crop rice growth in the early stage was better in azolla-treated plots than in no-nitrogen plots because of the carry-over of nitrogen from the previous azolla crop.

In the third rice crop, some plots were severely affected by boron toxicity. The toxicity was more severe in chemical nitrogen plots — hence yields were lower — than in azolla-treated plots.

In the fourth trial, plot size was 49 m² and distance between hills in 1 row was 13 cm. The average for four trials indicated that growing several crops of azolla in wide rows under a rice canopy and incorporating them gave about 1-t grain yield increase over the 0-nitrogen control. ■

Comparison of grain yields of azolla-treated plots and of plots with and without chemical nitrogen. IRRI, 1978-80.

Trial sequence	Cropping duration (from transplanting to harvest) and variety	Chemical nitrogen applied (kg/ha)	Azolla incorporations (no.) and nitrogen content	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		
				0 nitrogen	Chemical nitrogen	Azolla
1st	Dec 1978-Apr 1979 121 days IR26	107	6 crops, 105 kg N/ha	6.3 a	8.3 a	6.7 a
2d	May-Aug 1979 124 days IR42	60	4 crops, 70 kg N/ha	3.7 b	4.5 b	5.7 a
3d	Nov 1979-Mar 1980 104 days IR42	100	4 crops, 70 kg N/ha	2.7 b	2.2 b	3.6 a
4th ^b	Feb-Jun 1980 121 days IR42	60	4 crops, 70 kg N/ha	5.2 b	6.2 a	6.2 a

^a Any two means followed by a common letter are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level. ^b Field is different from the previous ones. One crop of azolla was grown before transplanting. Plant density was half that in the previous trials.

Environment and its influence

Supply of dry matter from stems to grain in rice grown under dryland conditions

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Studies on locally grown cereals show that flowering occurs about halfway through the crop's growth period in

maize and wheat but relatively later in rice, with grain development taking up a much smaller proportion of the growth period.

The relatively short grain-filling period in rice suggests either that good grain yields result from an accelerated crop growth rate after flowering, coincident with the development of the grain sink, or that substantial stored dry matter from other plant parts is translocated to

the grain during grain filling.

Three varieties, Blue Belle, IR40, and Brazos, which grow well in local dryland conditions, were sampled every 2 weeks for growth analysis.

In all the three varieties, crop growth rate reached a maximum at panicle emergence and decreased soon thereafter. In maize and wheat, crop growth rate reaches a maximum some weeks after anthesis.

Characteristics of 3 rice varieties. Chiredzi, Zimbabwe.

Characteristic	Blue Belle	IR40	Brazos
Sowing to panicle emergence (days)	85	106	95
Sowing to maximum grain dry mass (days)	118	146	132
Difference or grain-filling period (days)	33	40	37
Grain-filling period/total growth period (%)	28.0	27.4	28.0
Maximum dry mass of stems (g/m ²)	937	1029	1042
Dry mass of stems at the time of maximum grain dry mass (g/m ²)	623	578	528
Difference or loss of stem dry mass over grain-filling period (g/m ²)	314	451	514
Dry mass of grain harvested (g/m ²)	696	734	751
Loss of stem dry mass/dry mass of grain harvested (%)	45.1	61.4	68.4

A very large reduction in stem dry matter in the rice varieties after panicle emergence suggests that a very significant proportion of grain yield is derived by translocation of materials from the stems to the grain (see table).

The varieties were similar in proportion of the grain-filling period to the total life of the crop. Between 27% and 28% of the crop duration was used in grain filling in each variety, although maturity ratings ranged from 118 to 146

days. In the relatively short period of 33-40 days, grain yields of nearly 7 t/ha and higher were produced. Those yields were evidently achieved by translocation of stored materials from the stem and elsewhere, supplementing the normal crop growth increment in that period.

The evident loss of dry matter from the stems accounted for 45.1% of the grain dry matter in Blue Belle, 61.4% in IR40, and 68.4% in Brazos. That points to the importance of the stems' storage role in rice. In maize and wheat the loss of stem dry mass during the grain growth period is seldom 10% of the grain yield.

The considerable transfer of materials from the rice stems did not result in any undue weakening — no lodging occurred. ■

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